

DANIEL DEFOE'S "ROBINSON CRUSOE" AS AN EXTRAORDINARY EVENT IN THE HISTORY OF LITERATURE

Axmadaliyeva Dildora Farhodjon qizi

4th year student of English Language and Literature

Faculty of Fergana State University

Kosimova Mukammal Umaraliyevna

a teacher of English Language and Literature

Faculty of Fergana State University

ANNOTATION

This article is dedicated to the study of Daniel Defoe's world famous novel "Robinson Crusoe". The theme is very interesting and is worth of paying special attention. Uzbek readers enjoy reading the novel immensely. The book is rightly included to the list of masterpieces even created by Daniel Defoe. The author's work is estimated and read both by grown ups and children. Daniel Defoe founder of the early bourgeois realistic novel and he was the first and fore most a journalist, and in many ways the father of modern English periodicals.

KEY WORDS

Daniel Defoe, Robinson Crusoe, personality, novel, life, role of English literature, narrator, birthplace.

Daniel Defoe is famous was an English novelist, journalist and pamphleteer, famous for «Robinson Crusoe,» «Moll Flanders,» «Memoirs of a Cavalier,» and many other works. He was one of the founders of the English novel. Read more about the life and works of Daniel Defoe.

By Macmillan E. Novak. Oxford University Press. From the publisher: «Novak illuminates such works as Robinson Crusoe and Moll Flanders, novels that changed the course of fiction in their time and have remained towering classics to this day. And he reveals a writer who was a superb observer of his times—an age of dramatic historical, Daniel Defoe is perhaps best known for his novels, Robinson Crusoe and Moll Flanders, but he was also the quintessential «brilliant scoundrel» of the Augustan Age. In rough chronological order, Daniel Defoe was a hosier, soldier, wine merchant, factory owner, bankrupt, spy, pamphleteer, and convict, journalist, editor, political flunkey, hack writer and novelist.

The history of Robinson's life on the island is a story about creative work of a man, about his courage, his will, creative searching. This is a hymn to labor the source of life. Thanks to his creative work Robinson Crusoe remained a man. This is most remarkable and educative significance of the novel. The novel joined the elements of biographical documentary and adventure novel. The theme of creative labor should be emphasized especially Labor helped Robinson to stay a man in inhuman conditions of his life many years lonely in an island. There are very few selected books which can complete with this world known novel.

Daniel Defoe is not only the author of “Robinson Crusoe” he is the author of, as his researchers consider, about four hundred separately published works, polemic and publicist articles, pamphlets and so on. Which had been published by him in different editions. Creative energy of Defoe was extraordinary and almost unique for his country and his time, his people.

An unnamed editor explains his reasons for offering us the narrative we are about to read. He does not mention the name or story of Robinson Crusoe explicitly but, rather, describes the narrative as a “private man's adventures in the world” and focuses on its realism when he calls it a “just history of fact.” He claims it is modest and serious, and that it has an instructive value, teaching us to honor “the wisdom of Providence.” Thus, the editor asserts he is doing a great service to the world in publishing Crusoe's tale.

Robinson Crusoe occupies an important place in literary history as the first English novel and the forerunner of the realist tradition continued by Fielding and Dickens. There had, of course, been works of fiction prior to 1719 but these were not *novels* as we would recognise them today. What was new about Defoe's narrative was its convincing air of verisimilitude and the fact that its central character is a solid, believable individual with an inner life of remarkable consistency and power. Defoe himself draws attention to its verisimilitude in the Preface when he remarks: 'The Editor believes the thing to be a just History of Fact; neither is there any Appearance of Fiction in it.' The story has exercised a continuing hold on the human imagination; it has been translated into almost every language on earth and has even formed the basis of pantomime. Clearly, a story that has achieved the status of a fable must possess considerable literary and imaginative qualities and respond to some deep need in the human psyche.

Conclusion

Robinson Crusoe is in fact one of the great myths of Western civilisation, entertaining succeeding generations with its vision of a solitary Englishman on a desert island laboriously rebuilding a semblance of order around his lonely domain. As a 'desert island' myth the novel has spawned a multitude of imitations ranging from Ballantyne's *The Coral Island* (1857) to Golding's *The Lord of the Flies* (1954) and exercises an enduring fascination as a case study in survival. Today we no longer read the novel as a child's adventure story or a religious parable, but recognise it as a watershed in English literature and an allegory of the human condition.

REFERENCES

1. Daniel Defoe Robinson Crusoe McMillan Publishers 1997 pp.34-39, 45-49, 59-63, 128, 214-226
2. "Robinson Crusoe and his adventure" M. Prosveshcheniye 1973 pp.59,64, 78-79
3. Z. N. Shuravskaya About Daniel Defoe and his novel "Robinson Crusoe" L. Art Literature Publishing House. 1974 pp.56-59
4. J.Priestley Novel School in Britain Washington University Press W.2002 pp.17-46
5. History of the English Literature M. Prosveshcheniye 1971 pp.204-212
6. G.H.Healey The history of writing of "Robinson Crusoe" London University Press London 2001 pp.329-330
7. I.Turgenev Collection of works in 27 volumes Vol.26 pp.311-312.Readings on the English Literature M. High School 1978 pp.161-165
8. Г. Белинский Робинзон Крузо. Собр.соч. в 45тт. Т.44 стр.478-483